

Re-collection of *Senecio eminens* at KwaMandlangampisi

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Senecio eminens is one of those enigmatic species that I thought I would never see in its natural habitat during my research on the genus. Although it is a very distinctive species, only a handful of specimens from 4 collections exist in the SANBI herbaria. The last collection was made in 1961, the year of my birth, and now re-discovered in 2026, the year of my retirement. Apart from the scan of the type specimen no other illustrations or images have ever been published.

The species was listed as undescribed by Compton (1966) in his checklist of Swaziland and formally described by him in 1967. The specific epithet '*eminens*' is the Latin for 'standing out, projecting' and probably refers to the uniqueness of the species that stands out from the rest of the species in the genus.

Three of the known localities are in Swaziland and one in Mpumalanga. The Swaziland localities are given as Mbabane Distr., Mbuluzi Valley, and Mankayane Distr., 10 mi. W of Mankayane, while the Mpumalanga locality is in Iswepe in the Piet Retief Distr.. Due to urban development and forestry many of these original localities may no longer exist but one can still search for the species in remaining pockets of montane grassland in unexplored areas.

The newly discovered locality in the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment is well protected. Here it occurs on the slopes and in dry valleys of the mountains. Plants generally grow solitary and not in large clumps like many other *Senecios*, but in the two populations that were observed there were between 20 and 50 plants in each population. The area should be explored to evaluate the extent of the occurrence.

Fresh specimens with precise localities, images and DNA material are now available to better understand this species. The large discoid capitula of *S. eminens* is distinctive in the genus and can not be confused with any other species in *Senecio*. The figures below depict the species in its natural habitat. More images can be seen on iNaturalist. Please keep an eye open for this late-flowering species if you are doing fieldwork within its distribution area.

I would like to express my appreciation and thanks to Jeff & Lettie Morris for welcoming me into their piece of paradise, which made this discovery possible. Also to the great work the Mpumalanga Plant Specialis Group (PSG) do by introducing likeminded people to the magic of KwaMandlangampisi and many other special places.

References

Compton, R.N. 1966. Annotated Check List of the Flora of Swaziland. Journ. S.A. Bot., Suppl. Vol. VI.

Compton, R.H. 1967. Plantae Novae Africanae. Journal of South African Botany, Vol. 33, page 300 – 301

Figure 1: The whole plant showing the leaves that are mainly at the base, the sturdy and almost bare stems, and an open inflorescence of 3-6 capitula.

Figure 2: Leaves are smooth on both sides, with a strong midrib and attenuated bases.

Figure 3: Leaf margins are finely denticulate.

Figure 4: Capitula buds in the foreground with the back-drop of surrounding mountains. Note the robust capitula and very long calyx bracts.

Figure 5: A young discoid capitulum showing the yellowish florets.

Figure 6: An older capitulum with florets turning brown after anthesis, also showing the relative length of the calyculus bracts at this mature stage.